

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-2-113-IBN-5-2% rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	78	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 2 113
Injection Volume:	3.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	100.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	5/28/2022 21:13:00 CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 20:13:46 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.143	504378	16.88	45139
2	9.460	551255	18.45	42619
3	10.008	963223	32.24	71559
4	10.953	968509	32.42	67895

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-196-IBN-5-2% ASY	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	20230309
Vial:	76	Acq. Method Set:	2%210400
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	LRM 4 196
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	13.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/9/2023 9:05:18 PM CST		
Date Processed:	3/9/2023 9:31:21 PM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	8.831	18089622	94.38	1117375
2	9.609	22989	0.12	4850
3	9.935	332901	1.74	20027
4	10.944	722279	3.77	44048